

Naturally Urban? Tackling Inequalities in Urban Greenspace and Wellbeing

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Summary

This research aims to understand the relationship between greenspace, wellbeing and inequalities in England, using geographical and temporal weighted analyses of the UK Longitudinal Household Study and the Ordnance Survey Greenspace MasterMap. Results of pilot studies suggest a positive association between greenspace proximity and wellbeing, with strongest effects for more natural spaces. The results of the full analyses will provide a robust evidence base to inform future research and advance geospatial methods in the social sciences, while evidencing policies to address areas with the poorest greenspace provision and which have the potential to benefit most.

KEYWORDS: greenspace, wellbeing, accessibility, spatio-temporal analysis

1. Introduction

Neighbourhood effects matter for a range of behaviours and outcomes, including mental illness (Mair et al., 2008), physical (in)activity (Sallis and Glanz, 2009), and chronic conditions (Vigo et al., 2016). Increasing urbanisation and socio-spatial inequalities have spotlighted poor urban health, reinforcing the necessity for built environments to support wellbeing (Macintyre et al., 2002). Wellbeing represents an individual's experience of their health, encompassing individual emotional, functional, and subjective aspects, as a vital, yet often overlooked, component of a flourishing society; good wellbeing benefits individual satisfaction and emotional resilience, as well as societal longevity, productivity, and prosperity (Fredrickson and Losada, 2005).

Improving urban greenspace may reduce wellbeing inequalities, by connecting residents to the natural environments within which humans evolved and are best adapted to flourish (Wilson, 1984). Despite key policy targets of improving access to greenspace, especially in areas of deprivation or unequal provision, present understanding of what constitutes optimal 'access' is limited (PHE 2020), although use of greenspace is known to decline with distance (Ekkel and de Vries, 2017), and various forms may offer different salutogenic opportunities, including physical activity, socialising, and connecting with nature (Hartig et al., 2014). Furthermore, with planning policy distributed across multiple subsectors, there are no specific requirements for the amount, type, or location of greenspaces in England (PHE, 2020).

Moreover, neighbourhood factors, including physical, social, and environmental deprivation account for a seven-year difference in life expectancy across England (Marmot et al., 2010) and disproportionate access to greenspace (ONS, 2020); some communities are more greatly impacted by their environments than others, due to contextual or compositional factors (Houlden, 2019a). Integrating methods from social and geospatial disciplines, this research provides a novel approach to disentangling the contextual and compositional factors in the relationship between the environment and health, resulting in an accurate and detailed understanding of how greenspace may reduce socio-spatial inequalities improve wellbeing.

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1.1. Research Questions

This research aims to understand the relationship between greenspace and wellbeing in England, using geospatial analyses of longitudinal survey and map data, addressing three complementary research questions (RQs):

RQ1. How does greenspace access impact wellbeing?

RQ2. Which forms of greenspace are most beneficial to wellbeing?

RQ3: How can built and natural environments address wellbeing inequalities?

2. Methods

2.1 Data

Individual data are drawn from the UK Household Longitudinal Panel Study (UKHLS), an ongoing biennial data collection since 2009. It includes thorough socio-economic and demographic questions, alongside deprivation-experience variables (subjective financial situation, household-adjusted income), detailed wellbeing indicators (Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-Being Scale, life satisfaction, mental illness, general health) and lifestyle (physical activity, social contact, neighbourhood cohesion). Data from 2010, 2013 and 2016 are included for temporal analyses. The sample of residents in England with complete data is 18,000 individuals.

Designated public greenspaces are provided in shape files from OS MasterMap Greenspace layer. It contains polygons with the geographic location, size and type of urban public greenspaces across the country. OS Open Roads connect the data on individuals to greenspace in their surrounding area (Ordnance Survey, 2010).

Figure 1 Calculation of Individual Buffers

2.2 Analysis

To identify how greenspace access impacts wellbeing, greenspace quantity is calculated within Euclidean (straight-line) and network buffers of individuals' postcodes across England, at 300m, 500m and 1km distances (**Figure 1**). Linear and spatial regressions (Geographically Weighted Regression, GWR, Equations 1 & 2, **Figure 2**) are modelled with the 2016 data, to identify which generate an optimised indicator of greenspace availability, which is predictive of individual wellbeing outcomes (RQ1).

$$WB_i = \beta_{0i} + \beta_{1i}GS_{1i} + \dots + \beta_{mi}x_{mi} + \varepsilon_{mi} \quad (1)$$

$$W_{ij} = e^{-0.5\left(\frac{d_{ij}}{b}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

Where WB_i is the wellbeing outcome for individual i , β_m represent the regression coefficients for variables x_m , and ε_{mi} is the localised error term. The data points included in each individual-level model are weighted according to proximity; weights are distributed according to Gaussian kernel of bandwidth b , at distance d between individual i and each neighbour j , enabling to coefficients within the model to vary across space. The next stage statistically examines differences between those who have relocated (‘movers’) and those who have not (‘stayers’) between waves of the study, to identify potential effects of change in greenspace provision; controls for a range of socio-economic, demographic, and local-area deprivation feature in all analyses. The spatial distribution of association facilitates inference of additional underlying contextual factors.

Figure 2 Demonstration of neighbour weighting calculations

This model then extends to Geographical and Temporal Weighted Regression (GTWR), which computes weights according to the relative spatial S and temporal T positions of the data, at each time t , across data from 2010, 2013 and 2016 (Equation 3):

$$W_{ijST}^t = e^{-\left(\frac{d_{Sij}}{b_{St}}\right)^2} \times e^{-\left(\frac{d_{tij}}{b_T}\right)^2} \quad (3)$$

To model associations between different wellbeing outcomes and the main types of useable urban greenspace, four categories are stratified: natural areas, formal parks and outdoor sports facilities, and model moderation included by theorised mechanisms of social interaction, physical activity, and nature connection (RQ2). This facilitates consideration of temporal variation and the relative importance of the various greenspace characteristics.

Finally, spatio-temporal differences in access and outcomes for potentially disadvantaged groups are examined, according to gender, life stage, ethnicity, and local-area deprivation, creating opportunity maps to identify social, cultural, and environmental sub-groups most vulnerable to the poorest provision (RQ3). Trajectories of these indicators enable temporal geospatial regressions to model how relative change in social and economic circumstances interact with the association between greenspace and wellbeing outcomes, towards identifying causality and mechanisms of these relationships.

3. Results

While full analyses are ongoing, results of a pilot study reveal positive relationships between greenspace provision and wellbeing in London. The amount of greenspace available within 300m of residents was positively and statistically significantly associated with life satisfaction adjusting for socio-economic and demographic factors (global regression coefficient $B = 0.803$, ($p < 0.001$)). The strength of association decreased with distance, suggesting a potential ‘dose-response’ effect, with greenspace most important closer to homes (**Figure 3**).

Figure 2 The strength of the association between greenspace and life satisfaction in London decreases with distance (Houlden et al., 2019a)

Using Geographically Weighted Regression to account for the significant spatial clustering in the residuals of linear models reveals how the strength of these associations varied across the study area, implying that greenspaces may be more important for wellbeing in certain areas of the city, towards the West and outskirts of London, with weaker, sometimes negative associations detected in the centre (**Figure 4**). Comparing associations of different types of greenspace highlighted that natural areas demonstrated the strongest and most significant associations with hedonic wellbeing; this implies that nature itself may be more beneficial than artificially maintained parks or sports facilities (Houlden et al., 2019b).

Figure 4 The association between greenspace and life satisfaction varies across London (Houlden et al., 2019a)

The results of the full analyses will provide a robust evidence base to inform future research and advance geospatial methods in the social sciences, while evidencing policies to address areas with the poorest greenspace provision and which have the potential to benefit most.

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Biography

Dr Victoria Houlden is a Lecturer in Urban Data Science in the School of Geography, University of Leeds. Her research aims to understand the ways in which spaces and places embody inequalities, and the social structures influencing how people relate to their environment, particularly how urban landscapes impact wellbeing.